

Mobile phones in the dynamism of retail trade between Ivory Coast and Ghana; case of the cities of Bondoukou and Sampa

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Abstract

Initially set up to show the sovereign limits (boarders) of states, the borders have deeply been transformed into a dividing line. But they have been questioned both by the economic requirements consequences of globalization and by the human flux that cross them. So, the economic exchanges between Ivory Coast and Ghana through the cities of Bondoukou and Sampa are obvious.

The objective of this study is to conduct a micro-level analysis on the contribution of mobile phones to the rise of retail trade between the cities of Bondoukou and Sampa. The exploitation of documentary resources and semi directive interviews, organized with 13 transporters and 163 cross

border traders, revealed that the use of mobile phones is undeniable in their commercial activities, and has significantly amplified the cross-border trade to a small scale up to 52, 15%. Some socio-economic and spatial impacts have been noticed in Bondoukou and also in Sampa.

Keywords: Ivory Coast-Ghana, mobile phone-cross border trade-socio-economic impacts

Introduction

The mobile phone is a wireless means of communication, invented and popularized through the 1970s. It has quickly become the most means of communication all over the world, launched in the Ivory Coast in 1990 and two years later in Ghana, the mobile phone has known unprecedented rapid growth since the liberalization of telecommunications. This phenomenon, with numerous vectors, induced innovations and upheavals on economic, social, cultural, political and spatial planes. (Nassa & Manse, 2017: 8)

With its appropriation by the commercial sectors as a working tool, one asks himself whether the mobile phone could not contribute to the dynamism of trade, particularly the cross-border trade on small scale between Ivory Coast and Ghana through the cities of this Bondoukou and Sampa?

The objective (goal) of this study is to analyse the contribution of mobile phone use due to its different functionalities to the rise of cross-border trade to small-scale businesses with its spatial and socioeconomic coronary impacts.

Then, to reach this goal, this study is realized on three essential points. These points are as follows:

- The knowledge of the geographic area of the space of study and the uses of the mobile phone in such kind of trade,
- the mobile phone like a dynamising tool of cross border commercial exchanges, and,
- the socio-economic and spatial effects induced by the rapid growth of cross border commercial activity to a small scale.

Methodology

This study deals with the cross-border character of the trade between the Ivory Coast and Ghana. The target populations are the whole sedentary traders in the Ivory Coast and also in Ghana who exchange cross-border products. Considering the informal character of their activities, the traders could be mistrustful of the public authorities and any person unknown to their environment. They consider him as a state agent, fighting against counterfeit products and smuggling. That makes our population under study difficult to reach. Also, they are mixed with the other traders and are therefore difficult to be identified. To do that, the viral method is chosen for the collection of information. It is an iterative process of questioning.

It consists of questioning the first trader identified at the market owing to our knowledge of the environment or due to the trader union of the traders. This one introduces other traders, who after being interviewed, introduces other and soon, till the saturation point is achieved. The advantage of this technique is to establish confidence between the interviewer and the interviewee and make them feel that they are not taking any risks while doing their activity.

The sample is determined by the technique of survey with the answers in both cities (Bondoukou and Sampa) of the space of study. The enquiry is done in two phases. The first one from April 1st 2019 to April 5th 2019, was devoted to the identification of the cross-border traders and the second from April 20th 2019 to May 20th 2019, consisted of filling in inquiry forms. With the help of some resource persons, in the cities of enquiry, a certain number of cross-border traders were identified: 12 in Bondoukou and 7 in Sampa. After agreeing to take part to the inquiry, they are asked to distribute 10 questionnaires each to some persons in their neighbourhood taking part in the cross border trade on a small scale.

In summary, 190 inquiry forms were distributed.

After this phase, the questionnaires given to the traders were taken back and the difficulties were solved.

The table below, sums up the constitution of the sample (table 1). The software QGis, Excel, Word and GPS Garmin 64s were used to conduct this study. The software Excel permitted calculations and estimate proportions. The GPS Garmin 64s was used to geolocalise the working

places of the border traders. The QGIS was used to realize the map of localization of the zone under study.

Table: Constitution of the sample

Cities enquiry	of Sample	Number of enquiry forms given	Number of enquiry forms filled
Bondoukou	12	120	100
Sampa	7	70	63
Total	19	190	163

Source: ground survey, April-May 2019

Results

Presentation of the study space: Two spaces fastened to the border

The borders are geographical major facts. Their erection in a place, leads to a series of changes in the perception and relations of the spaces of societies or human groups directly concerned. The making out of a border, influences positively or negatively, a bit or deeply, the organization of the space or spaces that are adjacent to it. So around, the lines or the zones of the borders, some characteristic spaces are created and developed from the dynamic of the borders.

The space of study which geographic coordinates are on one hand 8°15'0" N and 3°0'0"W and 6°42'0"N and 1°46'60"W on the other hand, is the geographic space situated between the department of Bondoukou in Ivory Coast and that of sample in Ghana. Figure 1 as follows presents the space of study.

Sampa is a city in the region of Bono in Ghana, to the border with Ivory Coast. It is the capital city of the municipality of Jaman North which sheltered a slave market before. It was also the capital city of the Akan state of Gyaaman by the end of the 15th century.

The Jaman North municipal is one of the 12 (twelve) districts of the region of Bono in Ghana. It is located between 7°40'N and 8°21'N, and between 2°30'W and 2°60'W.

The location of the district along the borders between Ghana and Ivory Coast, presents some economic opportunities and potentials.

Like Siamese, the space is characterized by marketable activities that are manifested by the population exodus, that daily breaks the border to do their commercial activities. The cross-border commercial exchanges indicates “the cross borders attribute are done on both sides of the political

border of the states, that can be an intangible reality” and also permeable, and hopeful for the flux that can be encouraged or not by the administration”, in charge of the control and the management of this space. The cross-border commercial exchanges conditions a great part of the economic activities that are taking place in the cities that are directly concerned and even above. The economy of the space is based on the commercialization of agricultural and manufactured products. It is a homogenous space. This homogeneity is shown by the history, the sociology and the culture to which we can add an ethno-religious dimension. The challenge for this cross-border space consists of developing exchanges that are not only based on the differentials between the national systems. The cities of Bondoukou, Soko and Sampa play the role of integrator because the border between the two countries is open and pacified.

The Functionalities of Mobile Phones and Their Importance in Cross Border Commercial Exchanges.

The uses of the mobile phone are diverse and undergo changes in order to fill the needs of the moment. They touch the actors of cross-border small scale tradeoffs. So, this means of communication has improved in parallel with the technological evolutions, proposing new kinds of services.

The first improvement of the telephone remains in the continuity of services linked to communication, going from oral communication to sending messages.

The second great evolution of the mobile phone concerns the nature of services proposed, that welcome photography and music. The camera integrated into mobile phones, permits a new offer of communication.

The principal evolution of the mobile phone is the appearance of the smartphone. It opens door to new services, because of the nature of the numeric personal assistant with a service to sends and receives massages, access to internet. It is in this perspective of evolution, that the financial go-betweens create new types of payment adapting closely to the desires and needs of users. The mobile phone has turned into a very useful tool in the daily life of each person and a real tool of membership, of

identification or of social distinction, and seems to be a working tool for cross-border trade actors. The ground inquiries have proven that mobile phones takes a great place with the cross-border traders. In fact, the uses in cross-border of exchanges, and uses in cross-border commercial activities are indicated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The uses of the mobile phone for the cross-border traders of small

This chart shows the uses of mobile phones for the cross-border traders of small-scale businesses. It shows that out of the 8 uses people use it for, four take a great place and represent 100% (hundred percent). So, it is used not only to order goods, but also to receive goods orders, and get in touch with suppliers. It is also used as an electronic purse.

However, 98,77%; 96,32% and 82,82% of the cross-border traders of small scale businesses respectively use mobile phones to get informed about the availability of goods, or the prices and get in touch with customers. Otherwise, the services of « message » and « internet » are less used.

They represent only 11, 04%. With the technological mutualisation and the association of many processes of information diffusion, the cross-border traders of small scale have gone from a base practice to a specific use or more optimistic.

Before getting access to the mobile phone, most of the traders had to go to the regions of production in Sampa or Bondoukou every week to supply themselves. With the improvement of the mobile phone, no one has to travel twice or three times a month. That is a real spare of money and time.

The Mobile Phone, a Dynamising Tool for Cross-Border Commercial Exchanges

The mobile phone, through its functionalities, takes full part in the dynamisation of cross-border trade to a small scale, permitting the trader population in need of well-being to draw profit from the services linked to the uprising of this instrument of communication as shown in Figure 3 .

Figure 3: The benefits made by the cross border traders of small scale in the cities of inquiry with the use of the mobile phone.

Source: Personal inquiries on the ground, April 2019

The chart above shows that the mobile phone has given an impetus to the cross border commercial activity.

In fact, 97,55% of the interviewed remarked that the tool permitted them to handle properly their activity. While 52,15% affirm that it optimized their resources; 91,41% say to have quantified the profitability of the activity. 100 % of the cross-border traders think to have not only save time with the mobile phone; but it helps them to make quick decisions.

In sum, the adoption of the mobile phone in the cross-border commercial activity created a new value of use in helping the cross border traders

modify their habits and adapt their orders to their customers. Also, a good control of a great part of the orders and the details of supplying reduce the risks of the phenomenon of robbery and “road cutter”. It becomes possible to do business from a distance; in other words, it is no more useful to travel to agree on prices; quantities or how to deal with the date of payment of a transaction. According to these traders, the mobile phone deeply moved the situation of their activities these last years.

In fact, the appropriation of the mobile phone by the cross border traders permitted them to obtain a return on their commercial activities. According to the ground inquiries, when the question of the utility of the mobile phone in their activities was asked, all of the traders agreed unanimously that the about of the mobile phone has had a positive impact on their commercial activities. They assure to draw real benefits from its use. Also, they affirm that the advent of the mobile phone permitted them to boost their commerce activity as shown on the chart below that shows the profits made after the adoption of the mobile phone.

Figure 4: Some turn overs of the cross border traders in increase after the adoption of the mobile phone

Source: Personal ground inquiries, April-May 2019

The observation of figure 4 shows that the mobile phone took part in the increase of sales with a gradual increase of the cross-border traders' turnovers. They all agree that before the advent of the mobile phone, their takes were lower than that after the adoption of that tool of communication.

And also, to order goods they had to travel any time. On the socio-economic level, the cross-border traders say to invest their profits in properties and education and a great part of the family usually expenses.

Concerning the spatial drawbacks, they are seen in the source and the destination of goods. (Figure 5)

Figure 5: Exchange flux between the department of Bondoukou and Sampa

Source: DIVAGIS /our ground inquiries 2023 Conception: Sahoti OUATTARA Realization: Hino K 2023

Figure 5 puts out the spatial consequences of retail trade derived from the dynamism of the mobile phone. The volumes differ from origins and destination. The cities of Bondoukou and Sampa are grouping places for manufactured and agricultural products.

Essentially composed of manufactured products, the volumes of agricultural products are important from the city of Bondoukou to that of Sampa. The persons interviewed revealed that if only one product is intensely exchanged between the cities of Bondoukou and Sampa, it is the cashew nut. The principal Ghanaian actors finance ski patrolmen in the different localities of the region of Bondoukou, in order to purchase the cashew nut. Working in the unlawfulness, the purchases are done principally in the cities adjacent to the Ivory Coast-Ghana border, among others Tambi, Dèbango, Zagala, Sorobango, Kanguelé, Wolokei, Soko, Pinda, Boroko and Bohi. They come from Abidjan, the economic capital of Ivory Coast.

The transporters interviewed estimated the quantities of cashew nuts carried by trade in the city of Sampa to more than one hundred thousand tonnes. On the other hand, the agricultural products, namely yam, exchange product between the cities of Sampa and Bondoukou comes from the cities close to the city of Sampa while the manufactured products come from the city Accra and Kumasi.

Discussions

The retail trade between the two border countries has been “informal” trade, “non-registered”, “parallel”, “of smuggling” (Egg, Herrera 1998 p. 1). In this current study, it is defined as the whole exchanges of goods and services that are not registered in the official statistics of states and that integrate the reality of border crossing (Ayipam, 2010, p. 6. Mkinda & al, 2011 p. 24). These amounts evade generally the control and are not object of registration.

Fewer studies are however done on the contribution of the mobile phone to the dynamism of cross-border trade. This study is from that moment a contribution to enrich the literature. Since its advent, the mobile phone has nowadays penetrated all sectors of society (Fragoso, 2007, p. 1). That is why the cross-border traders are more and more exposed to the New

Information and Communication Technology (NTICS) while doing their activity- (Kanté, al 2017 p. 2). Many studies demonstrated that the advantages of the NTICS integration in commercial activity are real. With the NTICS, the information goes more quickly from now on and reaches the customers even at the most remote urban areas (Aker 2010, p. 3).

The advantages are in fact considered in terms of improvement of the decision making, because of the circulation of the information. These ones concern essentially the increase in the prices of the products (Ibrahima, 2008, p. 89). These advantages of the mobile phone have been put out by Aker in 2009 during his studies on the amelioration of the commercialization of the food crops and the living conditions of the actors in Niger and Ouganda. On the markets of Niger, he showed that the scattering of the price of the cereal to 10% and to 50% the costs of information seeking, giving way to more information on that of the food crops. These decreases induced an increase of the traders' incomes. Concerning Nassa, in 2012 he confirms the role of the mobile phone as a booster of global trade and dynamising the informal one. So, far from being an ordinary tool of communication, that creates closeness between people, the mobile phone has changed into a key instrument for the trade as a whole. And so, the informal trade offers itself an expressing place for the innovators network volunteer that developed some transactions, and externality generators. Despite all that, the mobile phone is not only seen as a communication instrument but also as a tool, outstanding the realness of the diversification of activities that have long ruled the world of informal in African cities. From that moment, the appropriation of the mobile phone by the cross borders facilitates the retail trade of small scale businesses. It permits to obtain a return from their commercial activities. This result is confirmed by NGoran K.A and Koffi Y. JJ'S study.

These authors demonstrated that it stimulates the dynamism of cross-border trade, permitting the actors to handle efficiently the transversal commercial flux that motivates this bordering country. It creates new commercial practices and permits the trader to obtain a return from their commercial activities. But the uses of the telephone in commercial activities are too many and differ from one trader to another. The

telephone has also put away the spectre of the distance, transcends it, lessens the movements and consequently maximizes the benefit (kombieni, 2016, p. 15). That makes Alzouma (2008, p. 8) say that with the mobile phone time and space are shortened.

The mobile phone contributed to the rapid growth of the retail trade, but this is not without special consequences. Gnamien (2002, p. 5) confirms this result.

Analyzing the impact of the development of the mobile phone in Abidjan's urban space, he discovers that the non-respect of settling rules of the public area creates an uricide, started by other practices so the striking consequence is away to an anarchical development of the city despite the help to the population.

Conclusion

The advent of the mobile phone, as a means of communication, has deeply moved the old commercial practices and infused a new dynamism to border commercial activities. But the use of the new technologies of communication in the border trade sector between Ivory Coast and Ghana varies according to the living place of the actors. This tool of communication favoured the fluidity of exchanges and has increased the efficiency and profitability of the retail trade. So, the consequence has been investing in properties, transport, and capacity building in investment. However, the special consequence has not been perceptible on both sides.

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